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Post Covid-19: Impact on Indian Business

Dr Bobby. B. Pandey¹, Neha Khilwani²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Guru Ghasi Das Central University, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, India

²Research Scholar, Department of Management Studies, Guru Ghasi Das Central University, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh., India

ABSTRACT

The Covid 19 pandemic has had a significant impact on businesses around the world. In Indian, the lockdown has resulted in a sharp decline in economic activity, with businesses forced to shut down and consumers curtail their spending. This has had a knock on effect on businesses, with many struggling to stay afloat. The pandemic has also highlighted the importance of digital transformation, with businesses that have digitized their operations faring better than those that have not. In the aftermath of Covid-19, there has been an increased interest in the fintech industry. This is mainly because it is a growth sector with an estimated CAGR of over 20% between 2019 and 2021. The industry is expected to reach \$700 billion by 2020, which means that it could become one of India's top three industries in terms of revenue generation within five years (according to McKinsey). In the post-covid-19, it is clear that businesses need to be agile and adaptable to survive. Those that are able to do so will emerge stronger and more resilient, while those that are not will struggle to stay relevant.

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CONTACT Dr Bobby. B. Pandey, Email: its.drbbpandey@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on businesses around the world. In India, the lockdown has resulted in a sharp slowdown in economic activity, with businesses across sectors

struggling to stay afloat. The situation is particularly dire for small businesses, which make up a large part of the Indian economy. Many small businesses have been forced to shut down due to lack of customers and cash flow. The

pandemic has also hit the Indian stock market hard, with the Sensex and Nifty falling by over 20% since the beginning of the year. The World Bank predicted that the Indian economy will contract by 5% in 2020 and have a severe decline in growth to 2.8% in fiscal 2021 in its South Asia Economic Update: Impact of COVID-19 report. The economic impact of the pandemic is expected to be long-lasting, with businesses expected to take years to recover. The global economy is experiencing its steepest decline ever. Nearly every country's growth has been significantly harmed by the corona virus, which is also to blame for the global GDP decline. India is similarly affected by this virus to other nations, however not as severely. Sales and income have decreased in almost every industry sector. India's GDP growth in the third quarter of 2020 was 4.7%. The government has announced a number of measures to help businesses weather the crisis, including a Rs 20 lakh crore stimulus package. However, it remains to be seen how effective these measures will be in mitigating the impact of the pandemic on the Indian economy.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the impact of covid 19 on Indian Business.
2. To study the business sectors which are most impacted by covid-19.
3. To study the future of Indian businesses post Covid-19.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology is essential for constructing the analysis work because both qualitative and

quantitative methods were included in the investigation. Secondary data, which was needed for this work, was gathered from textual sources such a variety of periodicals, articles, reports, books, journals, and literatures on the subject.

Impact of Covid-19 on Indian Business

The Covid 19 pandemic has had a significant impact on businesses in India. Many businesses have been forced to shut down, and those that are still operating are struggling to survive. The pandemic has also resulted in a decrease in demand for many products and services. This has had a knock-on effect on businesses, as they are forced to lay off staff or reduce their hours of operation. The pandemic has also caused a decrease in customer confidence, which has further contributed to the decline in business activity. In order to survive, businesses will need to adapt to the new reality of the Covid 19 pandemic.

The impact of Covid 19 has been felt particularly hard by small businesses, which often don't have the same resources as larger businesses to weather the storm. The impact of Covid 19 on businesses in India is likely to be long-lasting. Even after the lockdown is lifted, businesses will still be grappling with the effects of the pandemic. It will take time for demand to return to normal levels, and many businesses will struggle to recover. The Covid 19 pandemic is likely to have a lasting impact on the Indian economy, and businesses will need to adapt to survive in the new landscape.

Sectorial Impact

The business sectors most impacted by Covid-19 are those that rely on physical contact and close proximity. This includes sectors such as retail, hospitality, and tourism. The pandemic has forced many businesses in these sectors to close their doors, and others to dramatically change the way they operate. For example, restaurants have had to switch to take away or delivery models and retail stores have had to rely heavily on online sales. The pandemic has also had a major impact on the global economy, and this has flow-on effects for businesses in all sectors. Here are a few sectors that have been most impacted by Covid-19:

Retail

It's expected that the demand for cash in the system will be reduced due to a decrease in the usage of cash. This is because people are going to prefer using digital payments and other modes of payment such as credit cards, debit cards and cheques etc., which requires no physical currency.

This can be seen from an increasing trend of e-commerce companies offering their services online rather than through brick-and-mortar stores or even over phone calls. The same trend is also observed among small businesses that are opting for online sales rather than face-to-face meetings with customers. Retailers have been hit hard by the pandemic, as many consumers have been forced to stay home and shop online instead.

Real State

Real Estate is a big market in India. It has been impacted by Covid 19 and will continue to be affected by the end of Covid 19. Real Estate is an important part of the Indian economy, especially real estate properties that are used for residential purposes like apartments or houses. The government's decision to stop all manufacturing activities across India for two weeks starting November 26th 2019 will also impact Real Estate because there would be no demand for new construction materials during this time period.

Media and Entertainment

In the media and entertainment industry, Post Covid-19 has been a major challenge for all media houses. The impact of the virus on Indian television has been immense, as it has affected both advertising revenue and viewership.

The post-covid period saw a massive decline in viewership across all channels; however, there were some exceptions where ratings remained unaffected by this virus since they had already started airing their programs before availing themselves of post-covid services from their vendors for protection against such viruses.

Supply Chain

Supply chain is the process of moving goods from the point of origin to the point of consumption. It involves many players and processes, including production, transportation, distribution and retailing. In today's world economy, supply chains play a vital role in creating value for companies across all industries by enabling them to efficiently produce goods or services at low cost while meeting customer needs.

Supply chains depend on reliable infrastructure networks that enable seamless flow of products through multiple stages within a country or region without interruption or delay due to disruptions caused by natural disasters like floods etc., which have affected many countries since 2010 onwards after Hurricane Katrina hit New Orleans area causing major economic losses due to loss in productivity due lack power supply backup system failure during peak hour demand period

Healthcare

Healthcare is a big industry in India, and the country's medical community is expecting COVID-19 to have a positive impact on healthcare. The virus has been linked to higher hospitalizations and mortality rates among patients, according to international health organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO).

In addition to causing more deaths among people who are already ill or elderly, COVID-19 can also lead to longer hospital stays for those who don't experience any symptoms at all. This could mean that more people end up staying at home instead of going into an emergency room—and that's exactly what happened when people first started noticing signs of infection around their homes this winter season.

This trend may continue as long as there continues to be an increase in cases; however we don't expect it will affect all hospitals equally because different facilities tend not follow similar protocols when dealing with infectious diseases

such as influenza A/H1N1 virus or measles etcetera...

Future of Indian Business

The COVID-19 pandemic was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization about two years ago, and now the world is adjusting to the disruptions it has caused. The pandemic's toll on healthcare systems has been the most significant and lasting effect. And then there has been the economic toll, which has been more enduring and resounding.

Government initiatives to combat infections and stop the virus's spread resulted in supply shocks, particularly in manufacturing, while lockdowns and other containment measures caused significant business disruption. It is now obvious that the pandemic, which is expected to have long-term structural effects, has caused the globe to experience the second major economic and financial crisis of the twenty-first century. Additionally, it has exposed the weaknesses in the geopolitical and economic order of the world. In fact, our economy is starting to show signs of revival. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) predicts that the Indian economy will grow by 9.5% in 2021, while the world economy will expand by 6%. The adoption of widespread work-from-home policies, as well as the use of cloud services and videoconferencing, is all occurring at the same time that the world experiences exponential expansion in digital services and infrastructure.

Many technology companies have highlighted that it would ordinarily take two to three years to

make the gains in digitalisation that were made in a matter of months. Although there is still more work to be done, these are encouraging signals.

CONCLUSION

India is an exciting place for entrepreneurs and investors to do business. It is home to one of the fastest growing markets in the world with a rich culture, diverse people and a great diversity of products and services. The country is also well-known for its strong entrepreneurial spirit that has led it to become an economic powerhouse over the past few decades.

The COVID-19 pandemic has permanently changed how businesses run all over the world. The pandemic, according to 55% of survey participants, has "resulted in irreversible modifications to our organizational approach." A significantly higher 60 percent claim that COVID-19 has "advanced process automation" and "changed our approach to change management," while 64 percent acknowledge a shift to more cloud-based corporate operations. The corona virus pandemic and its detrimental economic implications made the statement that business's main social responsibility was to maximize profits while abiding by the law. This dictum, which places a sharp emphasis on the short term, has taken a firm hold on much commercial behavior. Business leaders will react to the effects of the corona virus outbreak in this environment.

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